

Key considerations to take into account for governance models of an open project given size, age, maturity level, resources, and total addressable community

Karthik Ram, University of California, Berkeley
karthik.ram@berkeley.edu

Introduction

This report briefly addresses issues related to governance (and organization structure) for groups that manage scientific open-source projects. In particular, I touch upon some of the tradeoffs associated with establishing any sort of formal structure. A key component of sustainability for an Open Source Ecosystem is having a robust process around decision-making and managing social collaboration, aka some form of governance. This issue suffers from having a lot of (disorganized) research on the topic, but not enough simple guidance on what governance model one must choose, similar to how GitHub has implemented the Choose a License (<https://choosealicense.com/>) website. While this boilerplate license chooser works for most projects, more complex projects will require open-source lawyers to draft their own license to meet specific needs and criteria.

Observations on governance in scientific open-source projects

Most projects don't realize that governance models can change over time as this depends on the ecosystem's life cycle. Projects can get by without any formal governance in the early stages, especially since they will not have many users when getting started.

There are various dimensions to governance in the context of OSS. They include ownership of assets, chartering the project, community management, conflict resolution, and the use of information and tools. Communities typically fall into one of three broad categories. These include open community, authoritarian community, and defined/organized community (Ritvo, Hessekiel, and Bavitz 2017). Scientific OSS projects typically fall under category 1 or 3.

Many projects default to the Benevolent Dictator For Life (BDFL) model (D, Cassandra, D

Hornbein, V Russell, N Schneider, n.d.), where one person holds the ultimate decision-making authority until a more inclusive structure is put in place. The Python Software Foundation operated this way till 2018 when the BDFL stepped down and the foundation adopted an elected board model.

From discussions with various STEM community managers and URSSI workshops conducted at 5 locations around the country, the general consensus appears to be that although the BDFL model (or similar where a project is led by a small group of founders) is perceived negatively (by its definition) it is preferred for early-stage projects since motivated founders with a clear vision can drive the project forward and get it past a certain stage before it falls off the rails due to lack of inertia.

Decision-making can exist at multiple levels in an ecosystem and can be governed by different models. These issues include:

- In the case of fiscally sponsored projects, who does the sponsor answer to? How does it make decisions?
- How can community members contribute to the governance of the overall community? e.g., steering committees, advisory boards, community council
- What does governance look like within the community i.e. within specific member-led activities such as working groups and special interest groups?

Even within BDFL communities, different models can operate at levels below and above.

Governance goes hand in hand with organizational structure and setup. Given the difficulties associated with setting up 501(c)(3) software non-profits, and the immense overhead that comes with administration, many projects have opted for other models (Ritvo, Hessekiel, and Bavitz 2017). These include joining existing non-profits as fiscally sponsored projects or setting up other corporate structures (Benefit Corp, S-corp, LLC). A good example of the latter is Julia Lang, the open-source data science language. It has a fiscally sponsored open-source project, and a separate Julia Computing business wing (<https://juliahub.com/>).

At URSSI and related initiatives, we see a two-step process to help software CoPs think about governance in a more organized way: describe the various models and offer simple governance templates to get started (see GitHub's minimum viable governance templates:

<https://github.com/github/MVG>, Community Rule templates:

<https://communityrule.info/templates/>). The structure offered here is sufficient for projects to have a formal decision-making process as they grow their technical stack and community. Governance becomes critical once projects reach a specific size, which can be defined in various ways such as the number of stakeholders, and/or substantial funding investments to grow staff/operations. At this point, project growth would be limited without formal governance. While some projects choose off-the-shelf models to emulate organizations of similar scope/mission, others seek professional help such as those provided by non-profit consulting agencies (e.g. LaPiana Consulting was hired by BioConductor to overhaul their governance setup).

Key readings

- [A Framework of Open Practices](#)
- [Community Rule Book](#)

Key insights and take-home messages include:

1. Governance is crucial for the sustainability of an open-source ecosystem, but there is a lack of simple guidance on choosing a governance model.
2. Governance models can change over time, depending on the ecosystem's life cycle. Early-stage projects often do not require formal governance, and benefit from more formalized structures once further traction is gained either indicated by a growing user base and/or increased streams of funding.
3. Key dimensions of governance in open-source software (OSS) include asset ownership, project chartering, community management, conflict resolution, and information and tool usage.
4. Scientific OSS projects typically fall under open community or defined/organized community categories.
5. Many projects default to the Benevolent Dictator For Life (BDFL) model, where one person holds decision-making authority until a more inclusive structure is established.
6. Decision-making can exist at multiple levels in an ecosystem and be governed by different models.
7. Organizational structures, such as non-profit, fiscally sponsored projects under non-profit, for-profit, or B Corp, and stakeholder makeup strongly impact governance.

8. Based on discussions at various URSSI working groups, I recommend a two-step process for helping software communities of practice think about governance more systematically: providing simple governance templates and seeking more formal guidance when projects reach a certain size or complexity.

Ultimately, governance is essential to maintaining a healthy open-source ecosystem and encourages projects to adapt their governance models as they evolve.

References

- D, Cassandra, D Hornbein, V Russell, N Schneider. n.d. *Community Rule Book*. Media Enterprise Design Lab.
- Ritvo, Dalia, Kira Hessekiel, and Christopher Bavitz. 2017. "Challenges & Opportunities Concerning Corporate Formation, Nonprofit Status, & Governance for Open Source Projects." <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2937956>.